

PROCESS OPTIMIZATION OF COMPOSITE PANELS WITH COMPRESSION MOLDING

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, the geometric conditions of precharge in compression molding process are optimized by simulation based genetic algorithm to improve mechanical properties of composite structure. Process simulation and structural analysis program coupled with fiber states such as fiber fraction and orientation are developed firstly. And genetic algorithm searches for the optimal precharge condition to minimize structural deflection. For handling constraints, both of penalty function method and repair algorithm modified for geometric optimization problem are suggested and compared. The repair algorithm is applied to an arbitrary shape structure to find optimal precharge conditions.

Keywords: *Compression molding, Fiber separation, Fiber orientation, Process optimization*

1 Introduction

The compression molding process is a manufacturing process in which precharges containing chopped fibers are compressed in a mold. In many cases, SMC (Sheet Molding Compound) in the form of a thin sheet is used. At the design step, the fiber state of the structure to produce is assumed to have a homogeneous fiber volume fraction and an isotropic fiber orientation at anywhere on the structure. This fiber's state changes due to the flow characteristics produced during the filling process. The mechanical properties of the final product are determined dominantly by this fiber state. Consequently, this non-uniform distribution of the fiber state induced by the fiber separation or the change of fiber orientation during the compression molding process generates non-uniform mechanical properties of the final product.

Some principal process parameters, such as the cure time, the mold closing speed, the molding pressure and the precharge specification (geometry, placement and size of precharge) affect the quality of the final product. Among them, the precharge specification is considered as direct parameter because it induces various flow patterns during the

process. In this study, both manufacturing process simulation and structural analysis were coupled to perform multi-objective optimization. And the location and dimensions of a rectangular-shaped precharge are considered as design variables to maximize the structural performance.

The generalized Hele-Shaw (GHS) model proposed by Folgar et al. [1] was taken for the 2D flow analysis of the compression molding process. The CV/FEM (Control Volume FEM) method was employed for the numerical scheme. Concerning the change of fiber volume fraction during the process, the fiber separation due to matrix-matrix and fiber-fiber interactions proposed by Yoo [2] and Hojo et al. [3] was used. To determine the state of fiber orientation, we used fiber orientation tensors proposed by Advani et al [4]. In order to predict the mechanical properties of a short-fiber composite based on the fiber state, was adopted Halpin-Tsai equation, which is the most popular model for estimating the mechanical properties of unidirectional composites [5]. For the structural analysis of plate, we used DRM (Discrete Reissner-Mindlin) element [6] for thin or thick plate based on Reissner-Mindlin assumptions.

In this study, to maximize structural properties of the final product manufactured by compression molding process, the processing conditions such as the location and dimension of precharge are considered as design variables in optimization problem. As optimization method, a Genetic Algorithm (GA) is implemented. Furthermore, the method to define the precharge location and dimension using a GA is presented. As technique for handling the constraints, a penalty function method and a repair algorithm, modified for optimization problems, are proposed.

2 Analytical and numerical modeling of flow and structure

For the GHS model used to analyze the compression molding process, it is assumed that the material is incompressible and the inertia is negligible because the flow in the thickness direction is negligible. The flow of filling process is assumed to be 2D. Due to the small thickness, only the variation of the shear stress in the thickness direction is taken into account in the momentum equation. The flow velocity is defined as the average in-plane velocity in the thickness direction of the material.

For the numerical analysis of fluid flow in this study, the fixed grid method is applied. To define the calculation domain and to obtain the flow front location, Volume-Of-Fluid (VOF) method is used. To calculate a more exact pressure distribution in flow front elements, FINE method is used [7].

To explain non-uniform distribution of fiber volume fraction in the final product, the fiber separation should be considered. In a concentrated suspension such as SMC precharge with a high fiber volume fraction, the fiber motion in flow is interfered by neighboring fibers due to the interaction between fibers. Thus, the reinforcing fibers may move at different speeds from the surrounding matrix. Due to the relative velocity between the fibers and the main flow, the initial homogeneous fiber volume fraction in precharge may become heterogeneous and thus make the final mechanical properties non-uniform. The network force, F_{nw} , which is defined as resultant of the frictional forces (Fig.1) acting on the fiber at different contact points with the neighboring fibers, acts as a resisting force and thus gives rise to the relative motion of fibers. The relative velocity of matrix to fiber, u_s , is defined as the difference between the matrix velocity, u_c , and the fiber

velocity, u_f . It can be assumed that the drag force on the fiber by the resin flow is balanced by the frictional force on the fiber. Therefore, the relative velocity can be determined by using the equivalence between the drag force and network force. And, the network force can be defined as the difference in the frictional force caused by the pressure variation acting on the fiber [2].

Fig. 1: Friction forces acting on fibers.

With the fiber velocity, u_f , the fiber volume fraction can be estimated by integrating the mass conservation of fiber for a control volume, assuming that the fiber content and the rate of fiber content change are constant.

A compact and general description of the fiber orientation state is provided by the tensors defined as follows.

$$a_{ij} = \int p_i p_j \psi(p) dp \quad (1)$$

$$a_{ijkl} = \int p_i p_j p_k p_l \psi(p) dp$$

where the unit vector p_i for two-dimensional orientation is defined as $p_1 = \cos \theta$, $p_2 = \sin \theta$ [4]. Note that a_{ij} is symmetric and its trace is equal to the unity. The advantage of tensor representation is that only a few numbers are required to describe the orientation state at any point in the space. For planar orientations, there are four components of a_{ij} , but only two are independent. An equation of single fiber motion for a concentrated suspension can be combined with the equation of continuity to produce an equation of change for the probability distribution function and/or the orientation tensor [8]. The result for second-order orientation tensors is described in detail in [9, 10].

By using the fiber volume fraction and fiber orientation tensors calculated from the processing

simulation, the mechanical properties of a composite structure can be estimated. Firstly, the properties of unidirectional material are estimated using the Halpin-Tsai equation [5]. Next, the mechanical properties of the final product are calculated by considering the fiber volume fraction and taking an average of the unidirectional properties over all directions. For structural analysis, flat elements were employed. A typical flat element is subject to plane stress and plate bending action. Therefore, the stiffness matrix is formed by assembling the plane stress and plate bending stiffness matrices. Also, the plate bending stiffness matrix is composed of two different stiffness matrices, which are obtained from bending moments and transverse shear forces. In this investigation, a triangular three-node DRM element is used for a plate bending problem [6].

3 Optimization of location and dimension of precharge

3-1 Optimization procedure

Because the precharge location and dimension can give significant effects directly on the fiber state according to various flow patterns, these were considered as design variables of optimization problem to maximize the structural properties. It is assumed that the precharge has a simple shape, e.g. rectangular shape, and that the precharge size is given so as to keep a constant mass after filling.

Because the objective function of our optimization problem is not differentiable or its gradient is not unreliable, direct search methods are useful because these methods are derivative-free. In this study, GA is chosen. The precharge dimensions and location are assigned as design variables, and it is necessary to generate a new mesh at each filling time step. Mesh regeneration has an advantage: the resolution of design variables can be modulated freely. For structural analysis, the generated mesh at the beginning is always used. To allocate the fiber state information obtained by the process simulation to the element nodes for structural analysis, a linear interpolation is implemented. Fig.2 presents the flow chart of the optimization procedure.

Fig. 2: Flow chart of optimization procedure.

3-2 GA coding

Both precharge location and dimension were considered simultaneously as design vectors, as shown in Fig. 3. Because the precharge dimension is not determined in advance, the range of the center of precharge location cannot be confined. Then, the entire mold area is defined as a possible region for the location of the precharge center (Fig. 3(b)). After setting one point of the grids as the precharge center, other grids for precharge dimension are laid on the point (Fig. 3(c)). Then, on this precharge dimension grids, the precharge is placed with the dimension generated by the dimension design vector. The design vector is defined as follows:

$$\bar{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) \quad (2)$$

where x_1 : grid number of the center in x-axis, x_2 : grid number of the center in y-axis, x_3 : grid number of the dimension in x-axis, x_4 : grid number of the dimension in y-axis. x_i with $i = 1, 4$ are integer which vary from 0 to 2^j with $j = 1, m, n, p$ for i varying from 1 to 4, respectively.

As shown in Fig. 3(d), if the precharge falls beyond the mold area, the process analysis cannot be carried out because the precharge must be completely located within the mold to keep the initial size for

process simulation. To treat infeasible solutions (i.e. precharge partially or fully outside the mold), some techniques to handle constraints are needed.

Fig. 3: (a) Mold shape and size, (b) Grids for precharge center, (c) Grids for precharge dimension, (d) Infeasible design solution.

3-3 Penalty method

Penalty method is one of the most popular approaches in GA. The approach assumes that:

$$eval(\bar{x}) = f(\bar{x}) - p(\bar{x}) \quad (3)$$

where $p(\bar{x})$ represents a penalty function for infeasible individual in maximization problem. The relationship between an infeasible individual and the feasible part of the search space plays a significant role in penalizing such infeasible individuals. In this study, the ratio between the precharge size overlapping the mold and the initial size is considered to present the penalty term as the distance from the feasible solution domain [11]. Therefore, the penalty function is defined as:

$$p(\bar{x}) = 1 - \frac{Area_{overlapped}}{Area_{designed}} \quad (4)$$

We inverse the displacement to have a stiffness maximization problem:

$$f(\bar{x}) = \frac{1}{d}, \quad d : \text{displacement} \quad (5)$$

It is impossible to evaluate the objective function f when an individual is in the infeasible solution domain, because the process analysis with an infeasible precharge condition can't be performed.

In this case, f is set as 0. In order to prevent the evaluation function from having a negative value, an additional value, 1, equal to the maximum penalty value, was added to f . Consequently, the evaluation function is redefined as given as

$$eval(\bar{x}) = Const + f(\bar{x}), \quad \text{if } \bar{x} \text{ is feasible,}$$

$$eval(\bar{x}) = Const \times \frac{Area_{overlapped}}{Area_{designed}}, \quad \text{otherwise.} \quad (6)$$

The closer the precharge size falls within the feasible solution domain, the higher becomes the evaluation function value. For this penalty method, a scaling scheme is used to redefine the objective function, f [9, 10].

Fig. 4: Flow chart of repair algorithm.

3-4 Repair algorithm

Repair algorithms are popular for many combinatorial optimization problems. A repaired individual can be only used for the evaluation, and the original individual can be succeeded or be replaced by the repaired one in the next generation. In this study, a repair algorithm is applied to handle the infeasible solution domain, in which the precharge falls beyond the mold area. Basically, the precharge dimension is repaired to maintain the initial shape as similarly as possible and the precharge location to be close to the feasible reference point [12]. The algorithm to repair the infeasible precharge location and dimension is composed of the following steps.

First, it checks whether the precharge size overlapping with the mold is the same as the original one. If they are the same, the evaluation function can be calculated for the original individual. If not, the repair procedure is performed. This repair procedure is described in detail in [9, 10].

Through this repair procedure, the initial infeasible design vector can be repaired to make it feasible. In this study, the repaired individual replaces the old infeasible one for GA operations. The procedure of the repair algorithm is illustrated in Fig. 4.

4. Examples

The verification and comparison of between penalty method and repair algorithm were done in detail on a simple case: rectangular plate [9, 10]. In this case, repair algorithm showed a slight advantage on the computational efforts than penalty method to find optimal solutions.

As industrial application, an arbitrary and unsymmetrical shaped structure in 3D was treated. As well as the precharge conditions, other constraints should be considered such as the air-void or weld-line formation during the manufacturing process. It is why, in this study, it is assumed that the air-void could be removed through vents and the fiber orientation could represent the weld-line if it happens. The material properties of the precharge and processing conditions are given in Table 2.

Initial fiber volume fraction	30 %	Fiber tensile modulus	72.5 GPa
Fiber length	25 mm	Fiber shear modulus	30 GPa
Fiber bundle diameter	2.5 mm	Fiber Poisson's ratio	0.2
Compression speed	1 mm/sec	Resin tensile modulus	2.62 GPa
Viscosity	500 Pa-sec	Resin shear modulus	0.984 GPa
Initial fiber orientation	random	Resin Poisson's ratio	0.32
Proportionality constant κ	0.5	Interaction coefficient C_I	0.04

Table 2: Material properties of the precharge and processing conditions.

The geometry and boundary conditions of the considered structure are shown in Fig. 6. Two

dimension of the precharge and two coordinate of the precharge location in x and y axes are considered as design variables. So, 4 variables are needed to be optimized. The objective function and constraints are defined as follows:

Fig. 6: Geometry and boundary conditions of the arbitrary shaped structure.

$$\bar{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)$$

$$\text{maximize } f(\bar{x}) = \frac{1}{d}, d : \text{maximum displacement}$$

subject to design constraints:

$$0 \leq x_c(x_1) \leq l_{dx}, 0 \leq y_c(x_2) \leq l_{dy},$$

$$0 \leq \frac{1}{2}l_{cx}(x_3) \leq \frac{1}{2}l_{dx}, 0 \leq \frac{1}{2}l_{cy}(x_4) \leq \frac{1}{2}l_{dy},$$

$$0.3 \leq \frac{Area_{Designed}}{Area_{structure}} \leq 0.7 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{Area_{Overlapped}}{Area_{Designed}} = 1$$

The obtained optimal precharge conditions and the searching procedure are shown in Fig. 7. Also, the distribution of fiber volume fraction and fiber orientation tensors calculated with the optimal precharge conditions is presented in Fig. 8.

Fig. 7: (a) Optimal location and dimension, (b) Convergence of 4 design variables for precharge location and dimension optimization.

Fig. 8: Distribution of (a) Fiber volume fraction, (b) Fiber volume fraction, (c) Displacement in z.

Through this example, we found that the repair algorithm is as efficient as the penalty function method for handling the constraints because the repair algorithm deals with the population in which every individual is feasible and no individual is thrown away. The modified repair algorithm is efficient for structures with a simple geometry. But it needs still other modifications for structures with a complex geometry, e.g. a structure with holes.

5 Conclusion

The optimization of precharge conditions in compression molding process was studied. To define the location and dimension of the precharge as a design vector, grids were implemented to determine its location and size. To treat this optimization, the whole search field of the design vector was divided into two spaces, the feasible and infeasible search spaces, because of the correlations of the design variables and constraints. To handle these constraints, a penalty method and a repair algorithm were implemented. In the penalty method, the penalty term was defined as the ratio between the precharge size overlapped on the mold and the original mold size. Concerning the repair algorithm, a modified repair algorithm was suggested. The repair algorithm is problem-dependent and it is necessary to be modified due to problem characteristics. In this study, only structures with simple geometry were considered. However, for a structure with complex geometry, the repair algorithm would need to be modified.

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